

Photoinduced *E-Z* isomerization across the imine bond in a multi-responsive organogel affecting morphology and structure[†]

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Abstract : A low molecular weight organogelator, (*E*)-*N'*-(anthracene-10-ylmethylene)-3,4,5-tris(dodecyloxy)benzohydrazide (OG) produces thermo- and mechano-responsive organogel in methyl cyclohexane. The organogel exhibits green fluorescent which is also retained in the xerogel state. The gel exhibits fibrillar three dimensional network morphology with average diameter 45 ± 8 nm. Rheological experiments reveal shear thinning and thixotropic properties of the gel. The fluorescence intensity of the gel is ~ 6 times higher than that of the solution with a 14 nm red shift indicating the J-type aggregate formation. On UV-irradiation at 365 nm *E*-isomer of OG transforms into *Z*-isomer in both gel and xerogel state and ¹H NMR spectra clearly points out the transformation. The kinetics of *E-Z* isomerization of OG in gel phase is carried out with duration of photo-irradiation at different temperatures by fluorescence spectroscopy. The rate constant values of photo-isomerization of the gels are obtained from the intercepts of Avrami plot and they are 0.16, 0.28, 0.31 and 0.49 min⁻¹ for 10, 20, 30 and 40 °C, respectively. The increase of rate constants with temperature indicates the process is Arrhenius type. The WAXS spectrum changes with UV-irradiation characterizing the formation of *Z*-isomer. On UV-irradiation for 24 h the fibers of OG gel transforms into microscopic crystals and the micro-crystallization occurs very fast in the xerogel state. The crystals are prominent in 4.5 h of UV-irradiation as evident from the bright birefringence pattern of the crystals with mostly dendritic morphology.

Keywords : Self-assembly, organogels, supramolecular structure, morphology, photoisomerization.

Introduction

In recent decade molecular self-assembly plays a crucial role in the development of functional soft materials¹. There are various functional supramolecules like organogels^{1,2}, hydrogel³, metallo gel⁴, dendrimers⁵, micelles⁶, and other soft materials¹, which are formed through molecular self-assembly. Amongst all these, supramolecular organogels have attracted a great attention because of their interesting physical properties and architectural classiness^{1,7}. Supramolecular gels consist of three-dimensional cross-linked networks, produced by self-assembly of the gelator molecules via noncovalent interactions, such as H-bonding, van der Waals, π - π stacking, metal-ligand, donor-acceptor and hydrophobic interactions^{1,7}, embedded in a solvent. Recently, supramolecular gels are extensively used in a number of areas, in-

cluding organic electronic devices⁸, catalysis⁹, sensing¹⁰, imaging¹¹, paints¹², delivery¹³, and control of crystal growth¹⁴. Gels are generally classified as chemical and physical gels according to the strength of the driving force involved in their formation. The chemical gels are usually tough and stable, whereas they are brittle, poorly transparent and it is unable to self-heal. In contrast, physical gels are weak due to non-covalent interactions and exhibit multiple stimuli-responsive behavior in presence of external stimuli such as light, heat, pH, solvent, ultrasound, enzyme, etc.^{1,15-20}. Self-assembled materials containing azo-moieties^{1,21}, have attracted tremendous attention because of their light-induced photo switchable properties. However, there are few examples of photo-responsive gelator molecules operating at the gel state through photoinduced *trans-cis* isomerization, because the

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trans-azobenzene moieties are tightly packed in fibrous gel superstructures²². However, the *E-Z* isomerization upon photoirradiation across the imine bond (C=N) in gel state is very exciting in the field of materials science. In this article we discuss photoinduced *E-Z* isomerization across imine bond of our newly synthesized (*E*)-*N'*-(anthracene-10-ylmethylene)-3,4,5-tris(dodecyloxy)-benzohydrazide (**OG**) in gel and xerogel states.

Results and discussion

A low molecular weight organogelator, (*E*)-*N'*-(anthracene-10-ylmethylene)-3,4,5-tris(dodecyloxy)-benzohydrazide (**OG**) (Fig. 1a), is synthesized encompassing an anthracene moiety attached to the 3,4,5-tris(dodecyloxy)benzohydrazide core. The LMOG is elegantly designed, so that it contains the H-bonding, π -stacking and van der Waals interacting motifs required for an organogelator. The **OG** organogel is yellowish green colored, transparent and thermoreversible (Fig. 1b), with a minimum gelation concentration of 0.05% (w/v) in methyl cyclohexane. The organogel is highly fluorescent (Fig. 1e), which is also retained in the xerogel state (Fig. 1d), and exhibits a mechanoresponsive behavior (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1. (a) Structure of molecule **OG**. (b) Schematic representation of mechanoresponsive and thermoreversible behavior of **OG** in methyl cyclohexane. (c, d) Digital image of **OG** xerogel under normal and UV light respectively. (e) Digital image of **OG** gel under UV light.

Structural analysis :

In the FTIR spectra (Fig. 2a) the $>C=O$ stretching peak of amide of **OG** powder at 1644 cm^{-1} has shifted to 1640 and the $-NH$ stretching peak of secondary amide of

OG powder at 3184 cm^{-1} has shifted to 3178 cm^{-1} in the xerogel. The shifting of vibrational stretching frequency both $C=O$ group and $-NH$ group of **OG** is because of intermolecular hydrogen bonding, taking place between the $-C=O$ group of one **OG** molecule with $-NH$ group of another **OG** molecule in the gel state. It is evident from the WAXS patterns (Fig. 2b) that pure **OG** powder exhibits some small peaks characterizing very low crystallinity which are absent in **OG** xerogel. The WAXS pattern of the xerogel shows broad peaks at $2\theta = 10.9^\circ$, 13.8° and 21.8° corresponding to d values at 8.0 , 6.4 and 4.07 \AA , respectively. The diffraction peak at $2\theta = 21.7^\circ$ corresponds to the π - π stacking distance ($d = 4.07\text{ \AA}$) in the xerogel.

Fig. 2. (a) FTIR spectra of **OG** powder and its xerogel. (b) WAXS patterns of **OG** powder and xerogel.

Fig. 3. (a) FESEM, (b) TEM and (c) AFM images of **OG** xerogel from 0.3% (w/v).

Morphology :

To investigate the morphology of **OG** gel, field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and atomic force microscopy (AFM) were performed (Fig. 3a,b,c). It is evident from the figure that the **OG** gel possesses three-dimensional fibrous network morphology. The average diameter of the fibers is 45 ± 8 nm and their length is of several micrometers. From a higher magnification FESEM image (Fig. 3a) it is apparent that the fibers are consisted of fibrils which are entwined with each other.

Mechanical properties :

Fig. 4 displays the rheological properties of the **OG** gel 1.0% (w/v) at 25 °C. Frequency sweep experiment of the **OG** gel is depicted in Fig. 4a which reveals that $G' > G''$ and is independent of the frequency in a wide frequency region, indicating the gel nature of the sample. Stress sweep experiments (Fig. 4b) of the **OG** gel is carried out to obtain the yield stress value of the gel. From Fig. 4b it is apparent that the values of G' and G'' crosses each other at an oscillator stress of 4 Pa indicating the breaking of the gel to a sol state. Fig. 4c portrays that the gel exhibits shear thinning behavior throughout the whole shear rate region signifying shear induced breaking of the gel.

Thixotropy is a fascinating viscoelastic property of supramolecular gels in which a gel is turned into a sol like material by mechanical shaking or stirring at isothermal conditions and it again returns to the gel state on standing. Some studies on thixotropic supramolecular organogels

based on naphthalenediimide²³, cholesterol derivatives²⁴, porphyrin derivatives²⁵, cyclodextrins²⁶, imidazole derivatives²⁷, dianthracene²⁸, urea²⁹ are reported in literature. Our newly designed **OG** organogel exhibits the unique property of thixotropy (Fig. 1b). For quantitative estimation of the thixotropic property we have performed time sweep rheological experiments under both a low strain of 0.1% and a high strain of 100% (Fig. 4d). At the first step a time sweep experiment is carried out at 0.1% strain where the value of G' is greater than that of G'' indicating the gel nature of the sample at a low strain. At the second step the gel is completely broken to a quasi-liquid state by application of 100% strain which is evident from the modulus values ($G' < G''$). At the third step the gel is allowed to recover by applying 0.1% strain and the modulus values ($G' > G''$) confirm the reincarnation of the gel. At the fourth step the gel is again converted to the sol state with 100% strain and is recovered in the fifth step. However it is noticeable that in the first, third and fifth step the values of G' are almost same which indicates that the **OG** gel is completely recoverable after being destroyed by mechanical force. For a gel to be certified as thixotropic, presence of long range interactions and driving forces for propagating in more than one dimension is indispensable. Both these criteria can be fulfilled by small molecular weight gelator with low crystallinity. Both the **OG** molecule and the **OG** xerogel have amorphous structure as evident from the XRD patterns which makes it thixotropic. The long fibers produced by assembly of the **OG** molecules are intertwined with each other at some junction points by the van der Waals type

Fig. 4. Rheological properties of the OG gel 1.0% (w/v) at 25 °C. (a) Frequency sweep data showing variation of G' and G'' with frequency. (b) Stress sweep measurement at a constant frequency 1 Hz. (c) Viscosity vs shear rate plot. (d) Continuous step strain measurement at alternate 100% and 0.1% strain with time scale.

interaction between the long alkyl chains causing the network. On application of mechanical force these junction points are ruptured causing the transformation to the sol state. Due to the presence of the alkyl chains in close proximity the van der Waals type interactions are again regenerated causing reformation of the gel.

Optical properties :

Fig. 5a displays the UV-Vis spectra of OG solution (10^{-5} M) and gel (0.1% w/v) in methyl cyclohexane. Two peaks at 367 and 387 nm in the absorption spectra of the OG solution corresponds to the π - π^* and n - π^* transitions of OG molecule. Both peaks are red shifted to 371 and 389 nm, respectively in the OG gel. This type of red shift in the π - π^* transition peak indicates π -stacking between the anthracene and benzene units during gelation which is also evident from the XRD patterns. Also the red shift in the absorption bands indicate the formation of J-type ag-

gregates in the gel state where the molecular planes are stacked side by side³⁰. Fluorescence spectroscopy is a powerful tool to comprehend the nature of aggregation in the gel state. Fig. 5b shows the fluorescence spectra of OG solution (0.025% w/v) and gel (0.1%) for excitation at 370 nm. It is clearly evident from the figure that the fluorescence intensity of the gel is ~6 times higher than that of the solution. Also there is a 14 nm red shift of the emission peak in the gel state than that of the solution indicating the formation of J-type aggregates during gel formation³¹. The OG molecule is fluorescence active due to the presence of the anthracene moiety. However, in solution phase there is a possibility of dynamic free rotation of the anthracene rotor which causes the non-radiative annihilation of the excited state. Consequently the solution state of the OG molecule is less fluorescent. In the gel state the molecules are closely packed by H-bonding and π -stacking interactions and the restriction of in-

Fig. 5. (a) UV-Vis spectra of **OG** solution ($10^{-5} M$) and gel (0.1% w/v) in methyl cyclohexane. (b) Fluorescence spectra of **OG** sol (0.025% w/v) and gel (0.1% w/v) for excitation at 365 nm.

tramolecular rotation occurs due to physical constraints. This type of restriction in the intramolecular rotation cre-

Fig. 6. Temperature dependent fluorescence spectra of **OG** gel 0.2% w/v for excitation at 365 nm.

ates a resistance to the non-radiative pathway thereby opening the radiative path for decay of excitons and the fluorescence intensity increases. A temperature dependent fluorescence study is carried out to reinforce our above hypothesis (Fig. 6). The fluorescence intensity of the **OG** gel decreases with increase in temperature and the peak position also gets blue shifted. A most probable reason is that with increasing temperature the inception of breaking of the self assembly occurs and after $\sim 500^\circ C$ the intensity decreases sharply due to the breaking of aggregated structure into single molecules.

Influence of photo-irradiation on the OG gel phase :

Change in electronic environment : The change in electronic environment of the **OG** molecule and to confirm its isomerisation upon photo-irradiation we have carried out 1H NMR spectrum of the **OG** molecule in $CDCl_3$ before (*E*-isomer) and after (*Z*-isomer) photoirradiation at different time intervals (Fig. 7a,b,c,d). In the 1H NMR spectrum of *E*-isomer (Fig. 7a), the methylene protons attached with the oxygen atom in dodecyloxy groups $[(-OCH_2-)]$ protons, indicated as 'i' appear at relatively downfield (δ 4.0–4.03) region due to strong electronic withdrawal of electronegative oxygen atom which are again directly connected with aromatic ring. Signal appearing at δ 7.18 is attributed to the ('h') protons. Four protons indicated by 'c' and 'd' are found at δ (7.44–7.52) showing a rather complicated multiplicity which is quite expected as both of the 'c' and 'd' protons should primarily show a double doublet pattern. A doublet signal at δ (7.98–8.0) is assigned to 'b' protons. Proton 'a' appears as a singlet at δ 8.47. The doublet signal at δ 8.59 is may be attributed to the protons 'e'. The broad signal at δ 9.61 is attributed to proton 'g' which is attached with electronegative nitrogen atom and is involved in H-bonding interaction here. Finally the most downfield signal at δ 9.71 is due to proton 'f' which is very much deshielded due to the coupled effect of paramagnetic anisotropic influence of (C=N) bond and very strong electronic withdrawal by electron deficient imine 'N' atom. Irradiation of **OG** molecule with photons (at 365 nm wavelength) at different time interval we got the *Z*-isomer finally after 12 h UV-irradiation (Fig. 7d), by photo-isomerization across (C=N) bond.

Fig. 7. ^1H NMR spectrum of OG molecule in (a) 0 h UV-irradiation (*E*-isomer), (b) 3 h UV-irradiation, (c) 9 h UV-irradiation and (d) 12 h UV-irradiation (*Z*-isomer).

In *Z*-isomer due to unfavourable orientations of anthracene moieties, π -stacking can't occur effectively and therefore 'electron delocalization' favorably occurs towards the anthracene ring. So, operation of electron withdrawing effect of carbonyl group on the phenyl ring splits the (-O-CH₂) group signals (at δ 3–4) of dodecyloxy groups. The ^1H NMR spectrum shows that (-O-CH₂-) signals in case of *Z*-isomer is split in two signals 'j' protons present in more deshielded environment comes at higher δ value (δ 3.81) than 'i' protons at δ 3.50 showing as expected 1 : 2 signal area ratio. Operation of electron withdrawing effect of carbonyl group also shifts the position of *ortho* protons (h) to downfield direction at δ 8.6, compared to the *E*-isomer. Now, in the *Z*-form due to increased steric hindrance, H-bonding with the (-NH-) hydrogen atom is not very much expected and this is reflected by the development of signal 'g' at much upfield region (δ 6.39). Now, absence of the above said H-bonding should place poor amount of (+ve) charge on the nitrogen atom of (C=N) of any individual molecule and this is reflected

by the relative upfield shift of the (-CH=N-) proton 'f' (δ 8.95). Proton 'e' and 'b' appears at δ (8.10–8.09) and δ (8.03–8.01) respectively showing doublet nature. Proton 'c' appears at δ (7.63–7.61) showing almost a triplet multiplicity as expected. However, the signal at δ (7.57–7.54) represents a complicated pattern with somewhat increased signal area than can be expected for 'd' protons. Therefore, this signal may represent a combined signal arising from the merger of signals corresponding to protons 'd' and 'a' as both of these two sets of protons are present in comparably electron shielded environment considering electronic delocalization of nitrogen atom lone pair of (-NH-) group within the anthracene moiety. So from all these studies it is well established that the molecule undergoes a *E-Z* type isomerisation across (C=N) bond upon UV-irradiation at 365 nm wavelength.

Change in optical properties : The photo-responsive-ness of the OG gel is studied by different spectroscopic techniques. For this study the gels are irradiated with a wavelength of 365 nm and the physical properties of the

gels are measured with respect to irradiation time. UV-Vis spectra of the **OG** gel at 0.2% (w/v) concentration (Fig. 8a) exhibits a decrease in the absorbance values and a concomitant blue shift in the $n-\pi^*$ transition peak with increase in photo-irradiation time. Amongst the two isomeric forms : *E* and *Z* of **OG**, the *E*-form is more stable and normally the compound is a mixture of the two isomers with the domination of *E*-form. With photo-irradiation with a wavelength of 365 nm the compound transforms into the *Z*-isomer. In the *Z*-isomer the intermolecular H- bonding between the -C=O group and -NH group becomes prohibited due to steric interference of the anthracene moiety. This disturbs the aggregation of the **OG** molecules which in turn prevents the π -stacking phenomenon. Hence the delocalization of the π -electrons and consequently the change in dipole moment value decreases. The transition moment integral also decreases causing the gradual lowering of the absorbance values with irradiation time. The blue shift in the $n-\pi^*$ transition peak with increase in photo-irradiation time occurs due to the disaggregation of the **OG** molecules.

The gels of **OG** exhibit an excellent fluorescence property arising mainly from the anthracene moiety of the compound. The change of fluorescence property of **OG** gel before and after photo-irradiation at 365 nm is because of the photo-isomerization of compound **OG** from *E*- to *Z*-form. The kinetics of *E-Z* isomerization of compound **OG** in gel phases is carried out with duration of photo-irradiation at different temperatures by fluorescence spectroscopy. Fluorescence intensity of the gel samples with irradiation time exhibits a huge change with photo-irradiation time at different temperatures. The driving force of photo-isomerization is UV-light, and the temperature may act as an additional stimulant in this photo-isomerization. Considering *E-Z* isomerization as a spring of the fibre-crystal phase transition we have used the Avrami equation on the fluorescence data to calculate the rate constant of *E-Z* isomerization (rate determining step) as the *Z*-isomers crystallizes giving birth of a new phase in the mother network phase³² :

$$\ln(-\ln(I_\infty - I_t)/(I_\infty - I_0)) = \ln k + n \ln t \quad (1)$$

where k is the rate constant, t is the time (min) of

Fig. 8. (a) UV-Vis spectra in a 1 mm cuvette cell and (b) intensity vs wavelength plot [Inset : Intensity vs UV-irradiation time plot] of 0.2% (w/v) **OG** gel at 30 °C after UV-irradiation at 365 nm wavelength at different time intervals.

irradiation, n is a constant related to the geometry of transformation, and I_0 , I_t and I_∞ are the PL-intensities at $t = 0$, t and ∞ . Thus, by plotting the left-hand side of the above equation with $\ln t$, straight lines are expected, and the rate constant k of the process is obtained from the intercept of the plot. Here, we are discussing the effect of irradiation time on fluorescence intensity of **OG** in gel states at four different temperatures. Gel state exhibits a good fluorescence due to its self-aggregation producing fibrils preventing the decay of excitons with the solvent (MCH) molecules. Fig. 8b indicates a sharp decrease of fluorescence intensity with irradiation time at 30 °C. The decrease in fluorescence intensity occurs for the disag-

gregation of the **OG** molecules upon photo-irradiation due to conversion of *E*- to *Z*-isomer. Here, the rate of photo-isomerization of **OG** gel is measured at different temperatures ranging from 10 °C to 40 °C using the Avrami equation (eq. (1)). Avrami plots obtained from the fluorescence spectral data of 0.2% (w/v) gels at different temperature are presented in Fig. 9 and the data fit well in straight lines with slope (*n*) values 0.55, 0.52, 0.47 and 0.4 for 10, 20, 30 and 40 °C, respectively. The well fitting of the data in straight line supports the applicability of Avrami equation in the transformation of fibrillar network of *E*-isomer to the crystallites of *Z*-isomer. The physical meaning of the *n* values involves a complex process of disaggregation of fibres through rotation of C=N bond followed by crystallization of *Z*-isomer. Here we approximate that the disaggregation process obeys the similar backward path with the growth process of ordered states for its reversible nature. Hence, the '*n*' values may be ascribed to the geometry that the disaggregation through rotation along the imine bond followed by crystallization and it may pass through a two dimensional heterogeneous process^{33,34}. The decrease of '*n*' with the rise of temperature may be attributed to that the process is diffusion controlled. The rate constant values of photo-isomerization of the gels are obtained from the intercepts of the Fig. 9 and they are 0.16, 0.28, 0.31 and 0.49 min⁻¹ for

Fig. 9. Avrami plot of **OG** gel 0.2% (w/v) at different time intervals upon photo-irradiation at 365 nm for different temperatures.

Fig. 10. WAXS patterns of **OG** in xerogel state before and after UV-irradiation for different time intervals.

10, 20, 30 and 40 °C, respectively. The increase of rate constants with temperature may indicate the process is somewhat Arrhenius type though the photo-isomerization of **OG** does not occur in absence of UV-light even if the temperature is gradually increased. Hence, it may be surmised that the temperature act as a promoter of light induced *E-Z* isomerization.

Change in WAXS patterns : In order to explore the change in packing nature of **OG** xerogel, the wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) study before and after UV-irradiation, is performed (Fig. 10). The WAXS patterns of xerogel, before irradiation, exhibit peaks at $2\theta = 10.9^\circ$ and 21.7° and a broad peak at $2\theta = 13.8^\circ$ with the corresponding *d* values of 8.0, 4.07 and 6.4 Å respectively. The diffraction peak at $2\theta = 21.7^\circ$ corresponds to the π - π stacking distance ($d = 4.07$ Å) as mention before (Fig. 2b). It is evident from the figure that, after UV-irradiation, the xerogel exhibits a number of new sharp peaks in its WAXS patterns which were absent in pure **OG** xerogel. The intensity of newly generated peaks gradually increases with increase in irradiation time, and the intensity of peaks for the native xerogel concomitantly decreases. From this result, it is surmised that a phase-change occurs from amorphous fibrillar network to crystalline structure under UV-irradiation at 365 nm wavelength.

Crystal formation from gel and xerogel state : Both gels and crystals are derived from identical methods, i.e. cooling the saturated hot solution when the molecules start to condense, forming either, highly order aggregates giving rise to crystals, or, comparatively less ordered aggregate producing gels. However, it is a very difficult task to produce crystals directly from the gel though equilibrium predicts that the crystal is a thermodynamically more stable phase compared to that of the gel, but the formation of crystals from the gels is very much kinetically controlled. It has been demonstrated that a gel phase converts into a crystalline phase over time and there are only a few reports regarding gel to crystal transformation. One most interestingly phenomenon is that, the xerogel transforms into beautiful crystals during irradiation which is a rare observation in supramolecular systems. Inspired from the WAXS results we visualize the crystal formation from POM studies. On irradiation of UV-light for 24 h the fibres of gel of **OG** transforms into microscopic crystals by keeping the irradiated gels

at low temperature (5 °C) for 3–4 weeks (Fig. 11a,b). It is noteworthy that the process of microcrystallization upon UV-irradiation occurs very fast in the xerogel state of **OG** (Fig. 12a,b) and the crystals are very prominent in 4.5 h of irradiation of the UV-light as evident from the bright birefringence pattern of the crystals with mostly dendritic morphology. This is a very interesting observation and can be explained from the molecular perspective. The *E*-isomer of **OG** forms a gel by intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the >C=O group and the -NH group followed by π - π stacking interactions. The gel consists of three dimensional fibrillar network morphology, as evident from the SEM images (Fig. 3a). So it is unambiguous that the fibres are obtained from the *E*-isomer and the crystals are obtained from the *Z*-isomer. The formation of two different type of molecular architecture is because of the different packing nature of the isomers. In the *E*-isomer, unidirectional growth is favorable due to the above mentioned H-bonding and van der Waals interactions. This unidirectional growth produces

Fig. 11. (a) Polarized optical micrographs of **OG** in the gel phase (a) before and (b) after UV-irradiation for 24 h.

Fig. 12. Polarized optical micrographs of **OG** in the xerogel phase (a) before and (b) after UV-irradiation for 4.5 h.

the fibers, leading to gelation. However, in the *Z*-isomer, this type of H-bonding is hindered due to steric inhibition of the anthracene moiety. So, the molecules are packed in more organized pattern giving rise to the crystals.

Conclusion

On UV-irradiation at 365 nm the *E*-isomer of **OG** transforms into *Z*-isomer in both gel and xerogel state and ¹H NMR spectra clearly points out the transformation. The kinetics of *E-Z* isomerization in gel phase is carried out with duration of photo-irradiation at different temperatures by fluorescence spectroscopy. The rate constant values of photo-isomerization of the gels are obtained from the intercepts of Avrami plot and the increase of rate constants with temperature may indicate the process is somewhat Arrhenius type. The WAXS spectrum changes with UV-irradiation characterizing the formation of *Z*-isomer. On UV-irradiation for 24 h the fibres of **OG** gel transforms into microscopic crystals and the microcrystallization occurs very fast in the xerogel state. The crystals are prominent in 4.5 h of UV-irradiation for the xerogel as evident from the bright birefringence pattern with mostly dendritic morphology.

Experimental

Materials : Methyl 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoate and 9-anthracenecarboxaldehyde (Sigma Aldrich Chemical Co.). 1-Bromo dodecane; methyl cyclohexane (Spectrochem Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai); hydrazine hydrate and potassium carbonate (Merck, India) were used as received. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (DMF) (Ranbaxy Pvt. Ltd., Delhi, India) was purified by distillation, and water was purified by double distillation before use.

Synthesis of (E)-N'-(anthracene-10-ylmethylene)-3,4,5-tris(dodecyloxy)benzohydrazide (OG) :

The (E)-N'-(anthracene-10-ylmethylene)-3,4,5-tris(dodecyloxy)benzohydrazide (**OG**) was synthesized and the details of each step is given below :

Synthesis of methyl 3,4,5-tris(dodecyloxy)benzoate (P₁) : Methyl 3,4,5-trihydroxy benzoate (1000 mg, 5.43 mmol), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (3300 mg, 23.87 mmol), *n*-dodecyl bromide (4362 mg, 17.5 mmol) and 20 mL dry DMF were taken together in a round bottom flask and stirred at 75 °C for 48 h under N₂ atmosphere. It was cooled to room temperature and poured into 125 ml ice-

cold water and was extracted with diethyl ether (3×25 mL). The organic layer was washed with brine (2×30 mL) and was dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure to get the crude product as light brown color solid. It was purified by column chromatography using basic alumina as stationary phase and 5% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether as eluent to get the pure product as white solid (3420 mg, 91.39%); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 7.27 (2H, s), 4.00–4.04 (6H, m), 3.89 (3H, s), 1.79–1.84 (4H, m), 1.73–1.76 (2H, m), 1.45–1.50 (6H, m), 1.27–1.35 (48H, m), 0.89 (9H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz).

Synthesis of 3,4,5-tris(dodecyloxy)benzohydrazide (P₂) :

Compound **P₁** (1000 mg, 1.45 mmol) and hydrazine monohydrate (3.6 mL, 72.54 mmol) were dissolved in MeOH (10 mL) and THF (3 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred at 70 °C for 36 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, and the volatiles were removed under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator. The residue was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ and washed with H₂O (50×3). The organic layer was then dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure to get crude product, which was purified by column chromatography using silica gel as the stationary phase and 5% MeOH in CH₂Cl₂ as the eluent to get the pure product as a light brown solid (920 mg, 92%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 6.92 (2H, s), 3.96–3.99 (6H, m), 1.71–1.81 (6H, m), 1.42–1.45 (6H, m), 1.26–1.29 (48H, m), 0.88 (9H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz) (Fig. SB); IR (KBr) ν : 3422, 3245, 2921, 2850, 1627, 1582, 1500, 1468, 1426, 1389, 1344, 1239, 1119, 844 and 720 cm⁻¹.

Synthesis of (E)-N'-(anthracene-10-ylmethylene)-3,4,5-tris(dodecyloxy)benzohydrazide (OG) :

A solution of 9-anthracene carboxaldehyde (119.6 mg, 0.58 mmol) in methanol was added dropwise to a CHCl₃ solution of compound **P₂** (400 mg, 0.58 mmol). The mixture was stirred for 2 h and the resulting product was dried under vacuum and then washed with ethanol to get pure product as a yellow powder (478.7 mg, 94%); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 9.71 (1H, s, CH=N), 9.61 (1H, s, NHCO), 8.59 (2H, broad, AnH), 8.47 (1H, s, AnH), 8.0 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, AnH), 7.44–7.52 (4H, m,

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AnH), 7.18 (2H, broad, ArH), 4.0–4.03 (6H, m, ArCH₂O), 1.73–1.78 (6H, m), 1.45–1.47 (6H, m), 1.26 (48H, m), 0.88 (9H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz) (Fig. SC); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 153.07, 144.54, 141.28, 131.41, 130.17, 129.38, 128.69, 127.89, 126.18, 124.82, 123.31, 105.51, 73.54, 68.86, 32.08, 30.35, 29.86, 29.82, 29.65, 29.52, 29.27, 26.16, 26.12, 22.84, 14.26 (Fig. SD); IR (KBr) ν : 3433, 3184, 3057, 2920, 2850, 1644, 1582, 1543, 1501, 1467, 1426, 1368, 1334, 1227, 1118, 1074, 1015, 840, 783 and 728 cm⁻¹; MS (MALDI-TOF) : *m/z* Calcd. for C₅₈H₈₈N₂O₄ : 876.67, Found : 877.655 [M+H]⁺, 899.640 [M+Na]⁺.

Preparation of organogel :

The compound **OG** (10 mg) was taken in a sealed glass vial and 1 ml methyl cyclohexane (MCH) was added to it. The glass vial was sonicated and heated to 70–80 °C to make a homogeneous solution that on cooling to 30 °C produces fluorescent, transparent, thixotropic gel. *T*_{gel} was determined by the dropping ball method (49 °C).

Rheology : To understand the mechanical property of the **OG** gel we have performed rheological experiment with an advanced rheometer (AR 2000, TA Instrument, USA) using cone plate geometry on a peltier plate. The diameter of the plate is 40 mm and cone angle 4° with plate gap of 121 μm.

Diffraction study :

The wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) experiment of xerogels and powder of compound **OG** were performed using a Bruker AXS diffractometer (Model D8 Advance) using a Lynx Eye detector. The instrument was operated at 40 kV voltage and at 40 mA current. Samples were placed on the glass slides and were scanned in the range of 2θ = 4–50° at the scan rate of 0.5 s/step with a step width of 0.02°.

Microscopy :

The morphology of the gels was investigated by transmission electron microscopy (TEM; JEOL, Model 2010EX). A small portion of the **OG** gel in methyl cyclohexane was diluted and was drop-casted on carbon-coated copper grid (300 mesh) and the sample was dried in open air at 30 °C. Finally, the sample was kept in vacuum for one day at 30 °C before the experiment. SEM image of

the sample was observed through a FESEM instrument (JEOL, JSM 6700F) operating at 5 kV after platinum coating. A small portion of the gel **OG** (in methyl cyclohexane) was placed on a glass coverslip and was dried in air at 30 °C for one day and finally in a vacuum. The AFM study was conducted using an atomic force microscope (Veeco, Model AP 0100). The texture of the sample was studied using a polarized optical microscope (Leitz Biomed) equipped with a digital camera. Then optical images were captured before and after UV-irradiation of the glass slide at different time intervals.

Spectroscopy : ¹H and ¹³C NMR data of synthesized compounds were collected on a Bruker spectrometer (¹H : 400 MHz and 500 MHz; ¹³C : 300 MHz). The xerogels before and after irradiation with UV-light were dissolved in the CDCl₃ to get the NMR spectra. The FTIR spectra of **OG** powder and the xerogel were recorded using KBr pellets of the samples in an FTIR-8400S instrument (Shimadzu). The UV-Vis spectra of the samples were recorded on a Hewlett-Packard UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model 8453) using a cuvette of 1 mm and 1 cm path length. In fluorescence studies of the **OG** gel samples were prepared in a sealed cuvette, and carried out in a Horiba Jobin Yvon Fluoromax 3 instrument. Each gel sample in a quartz cell of 1 cm path length was excited at 370 nm and the emission scans were recorded from 390 to 700 nm using slit width of 5 nm with an increment of 1 nm wavelength having an integration time 0.1 s.

MALDI-TOF : Mass spectra of **OG** solution in dichloromethane was recorded using MALDI TOF Ultraflextreme (Bruker Daltonics) instrument using Dithranol as matrix.

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References

1. S. S. Babu, V. K. Praveen and A. Ajayaghosh, *Chem. Rev.*, 2014, **114**, 1973.
2. S. Bouguet-Bonnet, M. Yemloul and D. Canet, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 10621.
3. X. Du, J. Zhou, J. Shi and B. Xu, *Chem. Rev.*, 2015, **115**, 13165.
4. M. M. Piepenbrock, G. O. Lloyd, N. Clarke and J. W. Steed, *Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **110**, 1960.
5. B. N. S. Thota, L. H. Urner and R. Haag, *Chem. Rev.*,

- 2016, **116**, 2079.
6. J. Brassinne, C. Mugemana, P. Guillet, O. Bertrand, D. Auhl, C. Bailly, C. Fustin and J. Gohy, *Soft Matter*, 2012, **8**, 4499.
 7. P. Terech and R. G. Weiss, "Molecular Gels : Materials with SelfAssembled Fibrillar Networks", Springer, Dordrecht, The Netherlands, 2006.
 8. P. Bairi, P. Chakraborty, A. Shit, S. Mondal, B. Roy and A. K. Nandi, *Langmuir*, 2014, **30**, 7547.
 9. B. Xing, M. Choi and B. Xu, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2002, **8**, 5028.
 10. K. K. Kartha, S. S. Babu, S. Srinivasan and A. Ajayaghosh, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 4834.
 11. S. Srinivasan, P. A. Babu, S. Mahesh and A. Ajayaghosh, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 15122.
 12. E. Carretti, L. Deia and R. G. Weiss, *Soft Matter*, 2005, **1**, 17.
 13. P. Chakraborty, S. Mondal, S. Khara, P. Bairi and A. K. Nandi, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2015, **119**, 5933.
 14. J. A. Foster, M. O. M. Piepenbrock, G. O. Lloyd, N. Clarke, J. A. K. Howard and J. W. Steed, *Nat. Chem.*, 2010, **2**, 1037.
 15. J. T. van Herpt, J. Areephong, M. C. A. Stuart, W. R. Browne and B. L. Feringa, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2014, **20**, 1737.
 16. D. Dasgupta, S. Srinivasan, C. Rochas, A. Ajayaghosh and J. M. Guenet, *Langmuir*, 2009, **25**, 8593.
 17. M. Liu, L. Zhang and T. Wang, *Chem. Rev.*, 2015, **115**, 7304.
 18. G. Zhu and J. S. Dordick, *Chem. Mater.*, 2006, **18**, 5988.
 19. J. M. Malicka, A. Sandeep, F. Monti, E. Bandini, M. Gazzano, C. Ranjith, V. K. Praveen, A. Ajayaghosh and N. Armaroli, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2013, **19**, 12991.
 20. Z. Dong, Q. Luo and J. Liu, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2012, **41**, 7890.
 21. J. Hatai and S. Bandyopadhyay, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2014, **20**, 10020.
 22. N. Fujita, Y. Sakamoto, M. Shirakawa, M. Ojima, A. Fujii, M. Ozaki and S. Shinkai, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 4134.
 23. A. Dawn, T. Shiraki, H. Ichikawa, A. Takada, Y. Takahashi, Y. Tsuchiya, L. T. N. Lien and S. Shinkai, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 2161.
 24. M. Xue, D. Gao, K. Liu, J. Peng and Y. Fang, *Tetrahedron*, 2009, **65**, 3369.
 25. M. Shirakawa, N. Fujita and S. Shinkai, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 4164.
 26. J. Araki and K. Ito, *Polymer*, 2007, **48**, 7139.
 27. W. Weng, A. M. Jamieson and S. J. Rowan, *Tetrahedron*, 2007, **63**, 7419.
 28. P. Mukhopadhyay, N. Fujita, A. Takada, T. Kishida, M. Shirakawa and S. Shinkai, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2010, **49**, 6338.
 29. J. Brinksma, B. L. Feringa, R. M. Kellogg, R. Vreeker and J. van Esch, *Langmuir*, 2000, **16**, 9249.
 30. V. Karunakaran, D. D. Prabhu and S. Das, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2013, **117**, 9404.
 31. A. Dawn, T. Shiraki, S. Haraguchi, H. Sato, K. Sada and S. Shinkai, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2010, **16**, 3676.
 32. A. Saha, S. Manna and A. K. Nandi, *Langmuir*, 2007, **23**, 13126.
 33. B. Wunderlich, "Macromolecular Physics", Academic Press, New York, 1976, Vol. 2, 147.
 34. L. Mandelkern, "Crystallization of Polymers", McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1964, 228.